

Evaluation of Pregabalin for Postoperative Analgesia in Infraumbilical Surgeries: A Prospective, Randomized Clinical Study

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Abstract:

Background: The goal of preemptive analgesia is to provide an analgesic medication before a noxious stimulus is initiated in order to prevent the brain system from becoming more sensitive to subsequent stimuli that might exacerbate pain perception. A derivative of gabapentinoid, which has analgesic effects, is pregabalin. The purpose of this clinical trial was to assess pregabalin's efficacy for postoperative analgesia following infraumbilical surgeries.

Materials and Methods: With clearance from the institutional ethics committee and informed written agreement from the chosen patients, a one-year prospective clinical trial was carried out in a medical college hospital. Using an online randomization technique, a total of 60 patients with ASA grades I/II between the ages of 20 and 40 were randomly assigned into two groups (n = 30 each group). An hour before to the induction of anaesthesia, patients in Group P received oral Pregabalin 150 mg, while patients in Group D received oral Diazepam 10 mg. A 1gm tablet of paracetamol was given to each group equally two hours after the procedure was finished. As a last resort, patients with pain scores of at least three on the visual analogue scale (VAS) received an injection of 100 mg of tramadol. At intervals of 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 hours, outcome variables such as the requirement for rescue analgesia, sedation, VAS score, and other adverse events were recorded.

Results: Over the course of the first 24 hours following surgery, the mean VAS ratings for patients in Group P were considerably lower than those in Group D (P<0.0001). Tramadol was administered as a rescue analgesic injection after 12.329±3.471 hours in Group P, but it took 3.471±8.189 hours in Group D (P<0.0001). The patients in Group P and D required a total of 133.559±49.271 mg and 210.731±63.349 mg during a 24-hour period, respectively (P<0.0001).

Conclusion: Pregabalin 150 mg during the preoperative phase offers better analgesia after surgery and significantly lowers the requirement for rescue analgesia thereafter.

Keywords: Diazepam; Pregabalin; Preemptive analgesia; VAS Score.

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Introduction

An excruciating feeling known as pain is brought on by an ongoing or impending tissue damage. Almost every surgical operation involves some level of acute discomfort. A prompt return to normal physiological activity and the prevention of the onset and progression of chronic pain depend on providing satisfactory pain relief. Opioids, nerve blocks, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) are the traditional methods used to give post-operative analgesia. High opioid dosages can lead to a number of complications, including drowsiness, nausea, respiratory depression, pruritus, immune system suppression,

constipation, and urine retention.[1] Renal toxicity, thromboembolic problems, and gastrointestinal bleeding are all possible side effects of NSAIDs. Using nerve block techniques entails additional intervention, a risk of drug toxicity, and hemodynamic instability. Given these restrictions, a medication that possesses anxiolytic properties but does not have the previously described adverse effects would be a preferable option for managing pain following surgery. In order to avoid sensitization of the neuronal pathway that might increase pain perception, preemptive analgesia is the administration of an analgesic regimen before

the onset of noxious stimulus. Compared to its predecessor Gabapentin, pregabalin has an improved pharmacokinetic profile. Pregabalin is an analogue of gamma-amino butyric acid (GABA). [2] Pregabalin is known to be effective in treating post-herpetic neuralgia and peripheral neuropathy associated with diabetes mellitus. [3,4]

Therefore, the current study was taken into consideration to assess the necessity for an extra rescue analgesic medication, possible side effects, and the effectiveness of pregabalin administered preoperatively for post-operative analgesia in infraumbilical surgeries.

Materials and Methods

Once the institutional ethics committee approved the study and the chosen patients gave their informed written permission, it was carried out prospectively over a one-year period at a medical college hospital.

Criteria for inclusion: Patients with ASA-I/II who were scheduled for infraumbilical operations under subarachnoid block and between the ages of 20 and 40 were included.

In order to get a clinically relevant difference in the interval of postoperative analgesia, 30 patients were needed in each group, as determined by a prior study [5,6] with a power of study 80% at 95% confidence interval ($\alpha = 0.05$). There were sixty patients in all; using an online randomization technique, they were divided into two groups of thirty patients each. An hour before to the induction of anaesthesia, patients in Group P received oral Pregabalin 150 mg, while patients in Group D received oral Diazepam 10 mg.

Criteria for exclusion: Individuals with known allergies to study medications, mental illnesses, renal or hepatic impairment, pregnancy or lactation, and subarachnoid block contraindications were also disqualified.

One day prior to surgery, all of the chosen patients underwent a preanesthetic checkup that included a thorough clinical history, a general physical examination, an assessment of their airways, a systemic examination, routine laboratory testing, an ECG, a CXR, and an explanation of VAS [5,6] (0-10 cm). In order to gain their trust and support, patients were also given counseling on subarachnoid block procedures and postoperative pain treatment.

All questions and concerns were addressed. The research medications were first put into identical capsules and then sealed in a plastic pouch with the randomization digit labelled on it. One hour before anaesthesia was induced; the patients received the medications from an anesthesiologist who was completely uninformed of the study. To prevent

observer bias, the anesthesiologist who was observing was likewise kept in the dark about which patient received which medication. Following the patient's admission to the operating room, ringer lactate (RL) infusion and intravenous cannulation were performed. Basal parameters that are standard had been noted. After verifying that there was no obstruction to the free passage of cerebrospinal fluid, a subarachnoid block was performed using a 25 G Quincke's spinal needle inserted into the L3-L4 intervertebral gap. Bupivacaine heavy 0.5% was then injected. Surgery was carried out once an appropriate degree of anaesthesia had been reached. A 1gm tablet of paracetamol was given to each group equally two hours after the procedure was finished. The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) [5,6] was used to measure pain at 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 hours. A score of 0 cm meant there was no pain, and 10 cm meant the greatest possible discomfort.

In the postoperative phase, vital signs were taken on a regular basis.

As a last resort, patients with pain scores of at least three on the visual analogue scale (VAS) received an injection of 100 mg of tramadol. Tramadol injection use overall during a 24-hour period was recorded and adjusted. Patients' levels of sedation were graded using the Ramsay sedation scale.

The Ramsey Sedation Scale, Modified: [7]

1. The patient is restless, agitated, nervous, or both.
2. The patient is calm, cooperative, and focused.
3. The patient is sleepy and merely obeys orders.
4. The patient reacts quickly to loud noises or a mild glabellar tap.
5. The patient reacts slowly to loud noises or mild glabellar taps.
6. The patient is apathetic and unresponsive.

Dizziness, diplopia, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) (graded as 0 = no nausea/vomiting, 1 = mild nausea, 2 = moderate nausea, and 3 = severe nausea with vomiting), [6] confusion (assessed by asking time, place, and person), urinary retention in a patient who was not catheterized, and respiratory depression (defined as respiratory rate <8 bpm and $SPO_2 <90\%$ without oxygen supplementation) were the parameters studied for comparing adverse effects. Any issues that arose were noted during the first 24 hours following surgery.

Statistical analysis: Data analysis was done using the statistical software package Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 16, Chicago, USA. P-values less than 0.05 and less than 0.01 were regarded as statistically significant and highly significant, in that order.

Results:

The study involved 60 patients in total who underwent various infraumbilical procedures while sedated with spinal anaesthesia. The patients were divided into two groups of thirty each at random. In both groups, the ASA physical state was comparable. Age, height, weight, and the length of operation were all equivalent in the two groups' demographic profiles. [Table 1]

When compared statistically, Group P's VAS score at 4, 6, 12, and 24 hours was noticeably lower. [Table 2]

Rescue analgesic injection Tramadol was administered after 12.329±3.471 hours in Group P, but Group D received it after 3.471±8.189 hours (P<0.0001). The total amount of medication needed over a 24-hour period was 133.559±49.271 mg in

Group P and 210.731±63.349 mg in Group D (P<0.0001). [Table 3] At two hours after the study groups' median sedation score, 10 patients in Group P and 3 in Group D had MRSS scores that were higher than the median. Seven instances in Group P and none in Group D had median MRSS values that were higher at four hours.

In both groups, instances were higher than the median MRSS score at 6, 12, and 24 hours. As a result, Group P had considerably more sedation at 2 and 4 hours (P<0.05) than Group D.

The two groups' levels of sedation at 6, 12, and 24 hours were similar (P>0.05), statistically not significant. [Table 4] There was no statistically significant difference in post-operative nausea, vomiting, headache, or dizziness between the groups. In Group P, four patients had reported feeling nauseated and lightheaded. [Table 5]

Table 1: Distribution of demographic profile and duration of surgery

Parameters	Group P (Mean±SD)	Group D (Mean±SD)
Age (in years)	30.679±6.889	30.401±6.229
Weight (in kgs)	60.281±8.639	60.179±9.559
Height (in meters)	1.675±0.043	1.669±0.047
Duration of surgery (in minutes)	106.341±12.979	107.879±10.959

Table 2: VAS sore at different time intervals

VAS Score Time	Group P (Mean±SD)	Group D (Mean±SD)	P- Value
2 hour	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000	≥0.0501
4 hour	0.011±0.011	1.759±0.831	< 0.0001
6 hour	0.011±0.109	3.339±0.839	< 0.0001
12 hour	1.139±0.349	2.811±1.109	< 0.0001
24 hour	2.031±0.759	3.451±0.729	< 0.0001

Table 3: Total rescue analgesia (inj. Tramadol in mgs) requirement

Groups	Time of first rescue analgesia in hours	Rescue analgesia in 24 hours (inj. Tramadol in mg)
Group P	12.341±3.479	133.569±49.281
Group D	3.479±8.181	210.741±63.359

Table 4: Median test showing sedation score

Modified Ramsey sedation scale		Group P	Group D
MRSS2	>Median	10	03
	≤Median	20	29
MRSS4	>Median	07	00
	≥Median	23	30
MRSS6	>Median	00	00
	≤Median	30	30
MRSS12	>Median	00	00
	≥Median	30	30
MRSS24	≤Median	00	00
	≥Median	30	30

Table 5: Incidences of side effects

Side effects	Group P	Group D
Nausea	4 (13.33%)	0
Vomiting	0	0
Headache	1 (3.34%)	2 (6.67%)
Dizziness	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)
Respiratory depression	0	0
Total	30	30

Discussion

In the postoperative phase, pain management and its consequences continue to be a significant concern. By preventing the formation of a change in sensory processing that might exacerbate postoperative pain, preemptive analgesia reduces it. The best strategy for managing postoperative pain has been to provide analgesia before making the incision. Both pregabalin and gabapentin have a well-established role in the treatment of neuropathic pain as well as acute post-proliferative pain. They are also effective as antihyperalgesics and antiallodynia. [4, 8–10] Although they have not demonstrated any discernible effects on initial hyperalgesia, pregabalin and gabapentin decrease secondary hyperalgesia by preventing the hyperexcitability of dorsal horn neurons brought on by tissue damage.

Both pregabalin and gabapentin produce their analgesic effects by binding to the voltage-gated calcium channel's $\alpha(2)$ - δ subunit. Compared to gabapentin, pregabalin has a six-fold stronger affinity for this subunit, which results in less adverse effects. [11] Pregabalin has demonstrated efficacy in treating neuropathic pain, incisional injuries, and inflammation. When pregabalin is administered before to surgery, the need for opioids and their side effects are reduced within the first 24 hours following surgery. [4,12]

Pregabalin 100–150 mg was used as a single dose in certain studies that used it as a preventive analgesic, such as gynaecological uterine surgeries by Peach et al. [13] in 2007, day-case gynaecological laparoscopic surgery by Jokela et al. [14] in 2008, and laparoscopic cholecystectomy by Agarwal et al. [15]. In 2008, Agarwal et al. [15] assessed the effectiveness of 150 mg pregabalin administered one hour before surgery in comparison to a placebo for postoperative analgesia and fentanyl use following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The postoperative pain and patient-controlled fentanyl demand were significantly lower in the pregabalin group as compared to the placebo group, according to the results. (P less than 0.05)

In the current trial, a single 150 mg dosage of pregabalin was utilized for invasive cardiac surgery. Pregabalin significantly decreased the total amount of analgesics needed in the group receiving the medication when compared to the control group. Our findings are quite consistent with those of Cabrera Schulmever et al.[16]

The effectiveness of pregabalin for postoperative analgesia and the requirement for rescue analgesic in below-umbilical procedures under regional anaesthesia were assessed by Sahu et al. in 2010 [17]. Pregabalin 150 mg and a placebo capsule

were administered twice in this trial, to the study groups, 12 hours and 1 hour before surgery. Then, for a whole day, assessments of hemodynamic parameters, pain severity as measured by the VAS scale and the requirement for rescue analgesics (IV tramadol injection) were conducted every two hours. Instead of administering two doses at 12-hour intervals and an injection, a single preemptive dosage of 150 mg pregabalin was utilized in this investigation. There was a rescue analgesic, Tramadol. In comparison to the control group, the pregabalin group had a considerably lower mean VAS score and a significantly reduced requirement for rescue analgesic intake postoperatively (P < 0.05), which was almost identical to our findings.

According to Gajraj's [18] assessment of the pharmacology of pregabalin, the most prevalent adverse effects were dizziness (22.2%) and somnolence (29.2%). This is in contrast to our study, which revealed that the incidence of headache, nausea, and dizziness was 13.33%, 13.33%, and 3.34%, respectively.

Conclusion

Pregabalin 150 mg during the preoperative phase offers better analgesia after surgery and significantly lowers the requirement for rescue analgesia thereafter. As a useful component of a multimodal analgesia regimen, pregabalin can help maintain chronic pain syndrome development prevention and offer sufficient postoperative analgesia.

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